

Odonata

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Extinct Geroptera: a plesiomorphic odonate order

Carboniferous, Argentina

Ancestral dragonflies had protowing-like separate radial sectors RA⁺ and RP⁺ (stem of R was absent). Veinal key characters shared with Paleozoic Ephemeroptera included: presence of strong recurrent ScA arch; absence of stem of R at wing base; fusion/struts between RP & MA, M & CuA, AA & CuP. Length 44 mm, with 11.5 mm.

+ GEROPTERA: Erasipteron cf. lunatum

Carboniferous, Argentina

THE OLDEST CARBONIFEROUS DRAGONFLIES BORE PROTHORACIC PROTOWINGS

Protowing veinal pattern on prothoracic wings versus of hydropaleopteran key characters enabling flapping flight on meso- and metathoracic wings indicates that aerial flight adaptation started at the protowing level (**not after** aerial flight was established, as often believed). Note that all five flapping flight enabling fusions of Geroptera are similar to those of mayflies.

HYDROPALEOPTERA: diversification of anterior articular plate

Ephemeroptera and Odonatoptera share as a key character the anterior articular plate

ODONATA

PROTANISOPTERA

PROTODONATA

EPHEMEROPTERA

Key to odonate forewing venation

Plesiomorphic dragonfly wing close to Odonoptera groundplan. *Eugeropteron* sp., +Geroptera, Carboniferous, Argentina. Wing venation is quite easily interpretable. Note that all important fusions/struts/braces are shared with Ephemeroptera: recurrent ScA; RA+ and RP+ protrude at base; MA base connected to RP; CuA base connected with the stem of M; AA 1+2 connected by a strut with CuP.

Eugeropteron lunatum, hind wing (counterimprint). Note that RA and RP are both + and separated; MA base is weak, and connected to RP with two struts; CuA is connected to M by short strut and AA 1+2 to CuP and CuA by a long strut. All these struts and near fusions are located in identical places in Ephemeroptera.

ODONATOPTERA - WING ARTICULATION

In all known Paleozoic adult and juvenile Odonatoptera, and in all adult Recent ones, the proxalaria (PR) are separate from the tergum. But in all Recent juveniles they are fused to the tergum. This shows that the wing organ originated entirely from the leg, but derived connections to the tergum, which sometimes improved survival, were added later.

Recent, Odonata: *Uropetala carrovei* New Zealand

Carboniferous, Geroptera: *Erasipteron* sp.

Fusion of winglets to terga in juveniles increased survival in thenymphs. It occurred already in the Paleozoic (in some Paleodictyoptera and in blattoids) and eventually prevailed. Paleoptera adults kept their wing organ separate from the tergum.

Fossil Hydropaleoptera: Odonatoptera show evolution of wing veins and sclerites

(± Meganisoptera)

Upper Carboniferous dragonfly nymph, *Alanympa richardsoni* (Meganisoptera) bearing articulated winglets shows original ancestral composition of the venation and the articulation in the anterior and posterior articular plate. Anterior plate shows basalare and precostal (PC) strip while costal (C) part includes axalare (AX) with a projection (nose) fused to fulcalare (F) composed of two lobes fused together and articulated to basivenale (B). Posterior plate shows six rows of sclerites (AX and F) fused together and to wing basivenale (B). Many characters are shared with Ephemeroptera.

Meganisoptera: *Meganeura monyi*, Upper Carboniferous, wing articulation.

All proxalaria (PR) abut the tergum (plesiomorphy). Axalaria (AX) are fused to fulcalaria (F), (derived). Fulcalaria of Sc, R, M, Cu, A, and J are fused also to wing basivenalia (B). Visible muscle attachments are indicated by little circles.

Key to "unsolvable" Odonata venation

Extinct Geroptera,
Upper Carboniferous, Argentina

Suborder Siphloformia
Infraorder Siphonurata

Siphonurus aestivalis

Siphuriscus chinensis

Odonoptera is the sister group of Ephemeroptera

Order Geroptera, Upper Carboniferous, Argentina
(bearing the plesiomorphic odonate venal pattern
and still movable prothoracic winglets),

Odonoptera share with Ephemeroptera all key wing
characters: recurrent ScA, RA and RP basally
independent (stem of R absent), stem of M and stem
of Cu present, and the following inter-venal braces
(struts or short fusions): MA near its base is connected
to RP; CuA to M; and AA1+2 to CuP.

Mirawara aapta

Siphonisca aerodroma

Carboniferous, Geroptera: *Erasipteron* sp.

Recent, Odonata: *Uropetala carovei* New Zealand

ODONATOPTERA - WING ARTICULATION

In all Paleoptera the proxalaria (PR) are separated from the tergum! This indicates that the fusion of some proxalaria with the tergum in (many but not all) modern Neoptera is secondary.

THE OLDEST CARBONIFEROUS DRAGONFLIES BORE PROTHORACIC PROTOWINGS

± **GEROPTERA: Erasipteron cf. lunatum** Carboniferous, Argentina

Prothoracic winglets were articulated, movable, and bore the protowing veinal pattern. But they were not adapted for flapping flight. This shows that pre-flight adaptation started already at the protowing level (**not after** aerial flight was established, as often believed). Note that all five flapping flight-enabling veinal fusions in extinct Geroptera are similar to those of mayflies.

Reconstructed body of adult protodonate *Meganeura* (Carboniferous, France)

Fig. 9. NYMPHS OF GIANT + PROTODONATA – BORE MOBILE WINGLETS

Young protodonate nymphs bore fully articulated winglets (Carboniferous, Illinois)

The fusion of winglets to the terga in modern nymphs is secondary.

Recent Dragonfly *Uropetala carrovei*
New Zealand

In Recent dragonflies, RA+ and RP+ became basally adjacent, the stems of M and of Cu fused together, and CuA and CuP fused to their origin together and also shortly to AA 1+2. This peculiar pattern remained un-interpreted for a century, and is still sometimes botched. Note that all Hydropaleoptera characters are nevertheless present, only quite hard to interpret without help from fossils.